

How Many Artificial and Intelligent Versions of Your Kid Do You Have Out There?

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Are we REALLY consenting to everything that we think we are, while using the internet and specifically social media? Have we actually read all the terms and conditions when we're using Facebook, Instagram, Google, and posting our pictures online? This is actually not new news; it's been a come-and-go wave of discussion, depending on how the tides turn to the big tech companies. Ok, so what's the big deal? Everybody is, or at least should be, aware of data, privacy, and sharing on the internet. The thing is, what about those whose digital privacy we're invading that are not even aware, nor choosing to do so?

Kids, right? That's what it's all about? YES, a thousand times yes. I remember when I was a kid, my parents and my friends' parents were quite protective of the use of the internet. Ironically, we used to take long hours' drive, bumping in the car seat without any seatbelts, and that's completely fine, your officer! Coming back to the internet, it does make sense they were suspicious, after all, that wasn't even close to a thing when they were kids. I remember that we were basically encouraged not to share anything online. Names, phone numbers, addresses, and (imagine) photos! The reason? A criminal could somehow get that information and do bad things to us.

On the matter of sharing, we went from scared anonymous to proud showoffs. We tell everything about ourselves; our real names, contact information, and we even share where we are at that moment, and we don't think about the bad guys doing bad stuff to us. The thing is, the danger now is not only physical, it's virtual as well. In the U.S. in 2023, consumers reported losing more than \$10 billion in fraud. It's not only the money; there's also identity theft, bullying, shaming, and WAY worse. Yes, pedophilia.

It took me a while to sit down and write about this. The reason is that it touches several aspects that are either very dear to me or that have my interest personally and professionally. The reason why I am writing about this now is that ignorance is bliss, and to this, I am no ignorant; I'm very much aware. In fact, I study, teach, and work with this. Many of us know the risks and protect our children from the evils that lurk in the corners of the internet. There's a catch, though, and it has multiple names, all built into the so-called Artificial Intelligence.

The wonders of AI and all the incredible powers that come with it. But remember, with great power comes great responsibility. The thing is, not everybody has a cool Uncle Ben. The bad guys also evolved, and they use technology to do bad things, right under our noses. All information we put online cannot be withdrawn. You can delete, but it will be forever stamped in the infinity tapestry of internet data. The same with images and photos. Not only ours, but our children's as well. Now imagine, if you ask someone not to post a picture of you for any reason, have you asked your kid if they allow you to post theirs? Are they aware of the invisible terms and conditions boxes they are clicking and consenting to, without even knowing how to read?

I know, I know, that's just being dramatic, or fear-mongering. Is it really? Have you tried the latest and most up-to-date AI tools out there? Have you seen what fake and imaginative images they can produce? Now imagine this falling into the wrong hands? "But Rafa, I'm not sharing body parts, nor nudity, not even skin!" - They don't need that. They just need a face. If we check our phones or social media, we will be surprised by the automation that face recognition identifies us or other people with so many random pictures. My phone knows my daughter's face way more than I would like it to. I consider myself overprotective sometimes, and I would say a couple of years ago that only pedophiles could see malice in a kid's photo. Now, way more evil people can. Before, they would imagine the body; now they can simply create it, with your child's face.

When I first wanted to write about this, it was right after seeing a campaign from Deutsche Telekom - A German Telecommunications Provider (I know, ironic, isn't it?). The video from the campaign, though, is quite interesting, and showcases to those less included in the digital, technological environment what we just talked about. The impacts of sharing our kids' pictures only. While it shows a rather terrifying scenario and is quite extreme, it is completely realistic and far from being fiction. I would like you all to reflect on this and to see this video. Let me know your thoughts after seeing it, or, if you have already, how impactful it was to you?

*Resources:

<https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/news/press-releases/2024/02/nationwide-fraud-losses-top-10-billion-2023-ftc-steps-efforts-protect-public>

<https://www.scamwatch.gov.au/research-and-resources/scam-statistics>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F4WZ_k0vUDM